

Using Fuzzy Classification System for Diagnosis of Breast Cancer

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Abstract: Evolutionary algorithms, one of important algorithms have been used in data mining field to induct fuzzy if-then rules based classification systems. Harmony search algorithm (HSA), an inspired algorithm from nature, has been successfully applied to classification. This paper proposes a rule-based system for medical data mining by using a combination of HSA and fuzzy set theory, we call it FHDD. In the classification problem the object is to maximize the correctly classified data and minimize the number of results. We have evaluated our new classification system via UCI machine data set. Results show the propose algorithm can detect diseases with an acceptable accuracy or even better than previous works. In addition, the computation time to build classifier reduce because of FHDD utilizes an HSA to learn a set of fuzzy rules from labeled data in parallel manner.

Keywords: Harmony Search Algorithm, Fuzzy Classification, Breast Cancer.

1 Introduction

Medical diagnosis can be viewed as a pattern classification problems: based on a set of input features the goal is to classify a patient as having cancer or as not having it, i.e. as a malignant or a benign case [1]. Breast cancer is the most common cancer in woman accounting for about 30% of all cases [2]. Most breast cancers are detected as a mess on the breast. Some diseases such as breast cancer show symptoms which

some of these symptoms are appear in the other diseases. Thus physicians must pay attention to previous decisions which made for patients in the same conditions, and whereas early diagnosis is important as it is directly linked with increased survival chances, thus the physician needs both knowledge and experience for proper decision making. From a computational point of view, breast cancer diagnosis can be viewed as a pattern classification problem: based on a set of input features the goal is to classify a patient as having cancer or as not having it, i.e. as a malignant or a benign

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case.

This job is not easy to consider the number of factors that the expert has to evaluate. To reduce the possible errors and help the expert, the classification system can be used. Classification is a supervised learning technique that takes labeled data samples and generates a classifier that classifies new data samples into different predefined groups or classes. This classification problem can be easily solved by fuzzy logic with interpretable if-then rules and membership function.

Classification schemes have been developed successfully for several applications such as medical diagnosis, speech recognition, etc. Classification problems, sets of if-then rules for learned hypotheses is considered to be one of the most expressive and comprehensive representations.

Generally the rules and the membership functions used by the fuzzy logic for solving the classification problem are formed from the experience of the human experts.

Because it is not usually easy to derive fuzzy rules from human experts, many approaches have recently been proposed to generate fuzzy rules automatically from the training patterns.

Expert systems and artificial intelligence techniques for classification also help experts in a great deal and for this reason; many algorithms are proposed to classify breast cancer.

The technique, which we have applied, based on fuzzy genetic learning. Several methods have been proposed to produce fuzzy if-then rules. For example, fuzzy rule-based classification systems are created by simple heuristic procedures [3,4], neuro-fuzzy techniques [5,6] and genetic algorithms [7]. One of the applications of GAs is pattern classification problems. Genetics-based machine learning methods for rule generation divided into two categories: the Michigan approach [8] and Pittsburgh approach [7]. In the Michigan approach, each rule is handled as an individual, called a classifier. The Pittsburgh approach [9] handles an entire rule set as an individual. In this paper, we have used Michigan-based algorithm for classification problem. To accomplish this purpose we have used a hybrid genetic algorithm with a harmony search algorithm.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes Harmony Search Algorithm. Section 3 describes fuzzy rule based classifier using GA and HSA. Experimental results are reported in section 4, and Sec-

tion 5 is conclusion.

2 Harmony Search Algorithm

The harmony search (HS) method is a meta-heuristic optimization algorithm firstly proposed by Geem in 2001[10]. HS algorithm is based on natural musical performance processes that occur when a musician searches for a better state of harmony. When a musician is improvising, he or she has three possible choices: (1) play any famous piece of music exactly from his or her memory; (2) play something similar to a known piece; or (3) compose new or random notes. In music improvisation, each player sounds any pitch within the possible range, together making one harmony vector [11]. This kind of efficient search for a perfect state of the harmony is analogous to the procedure of finding the optimal solutions to engineering problems.

3 Proposed Algorithm

In computer simulations, we used a typical set of linguistic values in Figure 1 as antecedent fuzzy sets. Then membership function applied to a fuzzy rule set are assumed to be isosceles-triangle functions and half-open trapezes as shown in Figure 1, where a_{ij} denotes the j^{th} linguistic value of Feature A_i . A total of 6 membership points ($z_{i1}, z_{i2}, z_{i3}, z_{i4}, z_{i5}, z_{i6}$) are required for representing each input variable as a fuzzy set. In that 6 points, first and last points (z_1, z_6) are fixed which the minimum and maximum of the input variable. To compute other remaining four membership points we divided distance between endpoints by 5.

Figure 1: Attribute Value A_i

Then we represent each membership function as a quintuplet $(P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5)$. If a_i is lower or equal z_{i2} then P_1 is 1 and P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5 are 0. If a_i is lower or equal z_{i3} then P_2 is 1 and P_1, P_3, P_4, P_5 are 0 and... An example in Figure 2 represents the process of encoding membership function sets.

Figure 2: The used antecedent fuzzy sets in the paper

S:	Small	10000
MS:	Medium Small	01000
M:	Medium	00100
ML:	Medium Large	00010
L:	Large	00001

3.1 Learning Fuzzy Rule

An HSA is applied to learn the fuzzy rules. So that, the learning process for each class is done independently. In other words, FHDD learns fuzzy rules related to each class in parallel way which cases decrease the time taken to build output classifier.

Outline proposed approach is as follows:

- Step 1: Generate an initial population of fuzzy if-then rules. (Initial Population)
- Step 2: Evaluate each fuzzy if-then rule in the current population.
- Step 3: Generate new fuzzy if-then rules by Harmony operations. (Rule Generation)
- Step 4: Replace a part of the current population with the newly generated rules. (Updating the Current Rule)
- Step 5: Terminate the algorithm if a stopping condition is satisfied, otherwise return to step 3.
- Step 6: Save the best individuals of the resulted population. Terminate the whole algorithm if a maximum number of iterations are satisfied. Otherwise, go to step 1.

Each of the above steps will be explain in detail

3.1.1 Initial population

Let us denote the number of fuzzy if-then rules in each population in our fuzzy classifier system by N_{pop} (i.e., N_{pop} is the population size). To construct an initial population, N_{pop} fuzzy if-then rules are generated by randomly selecting their antecedent fuzzy sets from the

five linguistic values. Each linguistic value is randomly selected with the probability of 1/5.

3.1.2 Evaluating each fuzzy if-then rule

The fitness value of each fuzzy if-then rule is evaluated by classifying all the given training patterns using the set of N_{pop} fuzzy if-then rules in the current population. The fitness value of the fuzzy if-then rule R_j is evaluated by the following fitness function:

$$Fitness(R_j) = \{\beta_{j1}, \beta_{j2}, \dots, \beta_{jh}\} \quad 1 \leq h \leq C \quad (1)$$

Where $\beta_{jh}(R_j)$ is the sum of difference of the training patterns (binary strings) in Class h with the fuzzy if-then rule R_j .

3.1.3 Rule generation

This algorithm learns rules for each class separately, therefore a fuzzy if-then rule is generated by generated rules and Harmony operations, for each class. A HMCR operation is applied to the selected fuzzy if-then rule with a prespecified HMCR probability. With a prespecified PAR probability, each antecedent fuzzy set of fuzzy if-then rule is randomly replaced with a different fuzzy set after the HMCR operation [12]. After generating of fuzzy if-then rules, the fitness value of each of the newly generated fuzzy if-then rules are determined.

3.1.4 Updating the current population

In our fuzzy classifier system, the worst rule with the smallest fitness value in each class is removed from the current population, and the newly generated fuzzy if-then rule is added if better. The above procedure is iterated until a pre-specified number of fuzzy if-then rules are generated.

3.1.5 Stopping condition

We can use any stopping condition for terminating the algorithm. In computer simulations of this paper, we used the total number of generations as a stopping condition.

3.2 Fuzzy Inference

Let us assume that our pattern classification problem is a c -class problem in the n -dimensional pattern space with continuous attributes. We also assume that M real vectors $x_p = (x_{p1}, x_{p2}, \dots, x_{pn})$, $p=1, 2, \dots, M$ are given as training patterns from the c classes.

When the algorithm generate fuzzy if-then rule for each class using M patterns, a fuzzy inference engine is needed classify test patterns. Figure 3 illustrate fuzzy inference engine [13].

Figure 3: The Testing Stage

When a rule set S is given, an input pattern $x_p = (x_{p1}, x_{p2}, \dots, x_{pn})$ is classified by a single winner rule R_j in S , which is determined as follows[14]:

$$\mu_j(x_p) = \max\{\mu_j(x_p) | R_j\}$$

4 Experimental Results

For evaluation of our proposed classification system we used from UCI data repository [15] such as Wisconsin Breast Cancer (Wisconsin), diabetes (Pima) and Heart. (Table 1).

Data set	Instances	Attributes	Classes
Wisconsin	699	10	2
Pima	768	8	2
Heart	270	13	2

Table 1: DATA SETS

The classification rate being calculated according to (2).

$$\text{Classification Rate} = \frac{(TP + TN)}{(TP + TN + FN + FP)} \quad (2)$$

Where

TP: true positives, the number of cases in our training set covered by the rule that have the class predicted by the rule.

FP: false positives, the number of cases covered by the rule that have a class different from the class predicted by the rule.

FN: false negatives, the number of cases that are not covered by the rule but that have the class predicted by the rule.

TN: true negatives, the number of cases that are not covered by the rule and that do not have the class predicted by the rule.

Also, Precision measures, Recall measure and F-Measure are computed by following equations. F-Measure is a trade-off between Precision and Recall.

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{F - Measure} = \frac{2 \times \text{Precision} \times \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (5)$$

Tables 2-4 show the mean classification rate, Precision, Recall and F-Measure for the generated rules by the proposed algorithm and several well-known methods, that have been tested by Weka software. Also because of the number of rules that our algorithm has proposed is low, this algorithm has good comprehensibility (Table 5).

Method	Classification Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure
C4.5	0.946	0.946	0.946	0.946
NN	0.958	0.959	0.959	0.959
KNN	0.951	0.951	0.951	0.951
BayesNet	0.96	0.962	0.96	0.96
Proposed algorithm	0.9778	0.978	0.978	0.978

Table 2: Wisconsin breast cancer data set.

Method	Classification Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure
C4.5	0.762	0.754	0.754	0.751
NN	0.753	0.75	0.754	0.751
KNN	0.702	0.696	0.702	0.698
BayesNet	0.743	0.741	0.743	0.742
Proposed algorithm	0.793	0.798	0.795	0.795

Table 3: Pima data set

Method	Classification Rate	Precision	Recall	F-Measure
C4.5	0.762	0.766	0.767	0.767
NN	0.751	0.75	0.752	0.751
KNN	0.735	0.713	0.732	0.728
BayesNet	0.811	0.811	0.811	0.811
Proposed algorithm	0.793	0.798	0.795	0.795

Table 4: Heart data set

Number of Rules for each class	1

Table 5: Result of algorithm

5 Conclusion

We have introduced a novel approach to fuzzy classification for medical diagnosis. This paper presents a mixture of Harmony Search Algorithm and Fuzzy Logic for classification. The proposed algorithm is used in the structure of a Michigan based evolutionary fuzzy system. The algorithm learned the rules for each class independently. Our experiments have confirmed that the algorithm can classify the data with considerable classification accuracy. The algorithm has some feature such as classification rate increase, to generate only one rule for each class or interpretability increase.

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